

LET'S TALK ABOUT IT

A GAME TO START **THAT**
CONVERSATION ABOUT
TECHNOLOGY WITH YOUR
FAMILY

Based on the results of the European
research project PlatFAMs

Co-funded by
the European Union

CHANSE.
COLLABORATION OF HUMANITIES
AND SOCIAL SCIENCES IN EUROPE

Quick Guide

This game is designed based on **real situations from families** across Europe that involve the use of digital platforms. **Anyone can play:** kids, parents, grandparents, relatives or friends.

How to play

1. **Pick a card and read** the situation aloud.
2. **Show the picture and read the questions** on the back.
3. **Everyone shares** their thoughts.
4. Choose **another card when you're ready** to keep talking.

The Goal

There are no right or wrong answers. The game simply helps families talk about digital life, understand each other better, and decide together how to use technology in a way that works for everyone.

Purpose of

the cards

The cards are designed to promote dialogue within families around the digitalization of their lives.

They were created **based on real situations** from Norway, Spain, the United Kingdom, Estonia, Romania, and Poland.

These situations emerged from fieldwork carried out as part of the **European research project PlatFAMs (Platforming Families: Tracing digital transformations in everyday life across generations)** funded by CHANSE/Horizon Europe.

Purpose of

the cards

The aim of these cards is to encourage families to discuss the topics that we have identified in our research as generating the most debates, dilemmas, or even disagreements within families.

If you want to **learn more** about the project and its results, you can read Section 5: To know more... and download resources and guidance from the website

<https://digitalfamilies.eu/>

DIMENSION 01

Communication

Situation

Sophia, mum Rosalía and dad Alexander are **sat on the sofa in the living room, each spending time on their phone.**

Sophia's friend just found out that some of her friends have a group chat without her, now Sophia is consoling her over text. Mum Rosalía is frustrated that she has been added to another birthday party group chat. She can't attend it and wonders whether she can leave the group chat immediately. Dad Alexander just heard about an upcoming school disco, and wonders whether he should put it on the chat for the immediate family, or the one with grandparents too.

Questions for

the family

- What is the purpose of **having different chats**?
- If you were added **into lots of different chats**, would it frustrate you or do you prefer to be included?
- How do you feel **when the family is on their phones** in a shared space?

Situation

Anna has an idea for the whole family to have a **half an hour video call every Monday**. She suggests a new video call app, which has lots of cool background features. This is best for her son, Philip, as he can get bored in long calls. **Grandad Anton spends an hour trying to work out how to log** into the calling app and feels embarrassed that he can't get it working. He doesn't want to ask for the family to help him, because he knows that they can get frustrated.

Questions for

the family

- How do you feel about **regular calls** with the whole family?
- Do you like **experimenting with new platforms**?
- Is it easy to ask other people **when we find technology difficult**?
- In this situation, how can the family **compromise**?

Situation

Grandma Olga shows off some embarrassing dance moves in the kitchen. The family is visiting, everyone is laughing with her, and **some family members are filming**. Father Alexander later shares his video on his social media, expressing how much he loved his family. Mother Rosalía has seen the post and feels unsure of how Grandma Olga would feel if she could access social media.

Questions for

the family

- How do you **share information about important relationships** in your life?
- Do you share funny things **about the family online?** Is intention important?
- Does it matter which **platform he used** to share the video?
- How would you feel if you **saw a similar video** of someone else's family?

Situation

Sophia's basketball team has just finished top of the league, and even though **she knows everyone is either at work or busy, she still wants to tell the family right away.** She texts her father that she's got exciting news to tell him.

She sees that he's read the message straight away, and after a few minutes he reacts a thumbs up to it. She sends a message to her aunt, and although she can see that her aunt is online, she does not respond straight away. She also messages her grandparents. Her grandfather calls immediately, but Sophia doesn't really want to talk to him and wishes he messaged instead. **She feels a bit deflated.**

Questions for

the family

- **Do you look to see** when people have seen messages, or are online? Why/Why not?
- How do you communicate when you are **busy**?
- How do you like to **share big news**?
- How would you **react** if you were Sophia?

DIMENSION 02

Intimacy

Situation

Sophia has just aced her exams. Feeling proud, **she posts a celebratory photo on Instagram** with the caption “Finally did it!”.

Her grandmother Olga, who isn't on social media, hears the news from a neighbour who saw the post. Later that evening, Olga asks: “Why didn't you tell me first?” Sophia looks guilty but also defensive: “I wanted to share it quickly... everyone posts things online.”

Sophia's mum, Rosalía, tries to calm things down but doesn't know whose side she should be on.

Questions for the family

- How do you prefer to **hear important news** from others in the family?
- How do you prefer to **share your own news**?
- **What kinds of news** would you like to share with each other privately before posting?
- What might **help people in our family to feel more included** in the future?

Situation

At the Fernandez family dinner, **the table is full of chatter**. Jan and Granddad Anton are laughing as they play a quick quiz game with Alexa. Dad Alexander sits nearby and tries to tell everyone a funny story from work. Meanwhile, Mum Rosalía glances down repeatedly at her phone as work messages keep popping up. She tries to listen in, but the group moves on without her.

Dad Alexander **eventually stops mid-story, unsure who is paying attention**. Rosalía feels pulled in different directions: wanting to join in, but also feeling pressure to respond to work. Jan and granddad stop the game a bit disappointed.

Questions for

the family

- What helps each of you feel included during **shared time like meals**?
- When does a message **feel important enough** to answer straight away?
- What kinds of **digital interruptions** feel fine to you, and which ones feel disruptive?
- Would you enjoy having **any shared mealtime rules** and why? If yes, what might they look like?

Situation

Jan goes to his parent-teacher meeting with Granddad Anton, while **his dad Alexander joins by video call from work**. The connection keeps freezing, and Alexander misses parts of the conversation. Jan is glad he tried to be there, but also wishes he could talk to his dad in the same room like other families.

Questions for

the family

- What does “**being present**” mean to each of you during important moments?
- When does **joining by video feel good enough**, and when does it feel disappointing?
- **If someone** can only join remotely, what could help make that feel more connected?
- How do you each **want to be supported** during big school or family events?

Situation

After a disagreement about chores, sixteen-year-old Sophia **heads straight to her room and lies on her bed, scrolling through videos** instead of doing what she was asked. Her mum Rosalía, feels frustrated – she wants the chores done, but she also wonders if pushing her right now will make things worse.

She stands at the doorway, unsure whether to give her a bit of space or insist she gets started. Grandma Olga, listening from the living room, quietly wonders whether the screen is helping Sophia unwind or keeping her from talking about what's really bothering her. She wonders if she should message her to make sure she is OK.

Questions for

the family

- **What do each of you need** after an argument — space, talking, distraction, something else?
- When does going on a device **help you calm down**? When does it feel unhelpful or lonely?
- How can you **let others know** when you need time alone?
- **How would you like** someone to check in with you after a disagreement?

DIMENSION 03

Surveillance

Situation

Sophia is 16 years old and she went to a party. **She agreed to come home at 23h, but she hasn't returned yet.** Rosalía, her mother, is concerned and she is considering using an app that tracks location to see where Sophia is.

Questions for

the family

- **How do you think Sophia would feel** if her mum decided to track her location?
- **Have you ever talked about the possibility of using geolocation apps** to know where other family members are?
- If you know where each of you are all the time, does that mean **the platform owners know as well?** If so, how does that make you feel?
- As a family, **would you like to have an agreement** about using these apps?

Situation

Philip is 11 years old. Philip's grandmother wants to **track him** through an app on his phone when Philip goes outside while he is visiting his grandmother. **Philip does not want his grandmother to track him.**

Questions for

the family

- Why do you think **Philip's grandmother wants to track him?**
- Why do you think Philip **does not want** to be tracked?
- What do you think Philip **feels when he is being tracked?**

Situation

Alexander is doing everything he can to **avoid using Google**, but his son's school has required his 8-year-old son Jan to create a Google account in order to use Google Classroom.

Questions for

the family

- Why do you think Alexander **doesn't** want to use Google?
- **Should schools be allowed** to require minors to create accounts with corporations like Google?
- What **possibilities are for parents** to do something about this?

Situation

Alexander has defined a circle on the map of a geolocation app on his phone, which sends him an alarm if his son Jan leaves the playground in the park nearby.

Alexander thinks this is very practical, because **he can do other things in the house while Jan is playing in the park. He uses the app because it is safer for Jan.**

Questions for

the family

- What do you think changes in Alexander and Jan's relationship due to the **use of the geolocation platform?**
- **What would you do in this situation?**

DIMENSION 04

Streaming & Gaming

Situation

In the afternoon, Grandfather Anton was looking after his youngest grandson, Jan. When Jan's father Alexander comes home from work, Anton suggests that the **three of them watch a film from his youth**, which he recently managed to find in a streaming platform's library.

However, Jan would prefer that they watch **a new video from his favourite YouTuber together**. Alexander, on the other hand, argues that since they so rarely have the chance to spend an evening together, it would be more valuable to talk.

Questions for

the family

- **Why do you think** Alexander prefers talking over watching something together? Why might grandfather care about watching an old film? And what might make the grandson want to watch his favourite YouTuber with his dad and grandfather?
- How could they reach **an agreement** on how to spend time together?
- What is **important for your own family** when you spend time together?

Situation

A family decides to **play games together on a Wednesday after school**. Philip suggests they play a multiplayer game on the Nintendo in the living room. His mother Anna believes they should play a boardgame and proposes that that's better for them.

Questions for

the family

→ **Games can be both digital and non-digital.** Is one better than the other when it comes to family spending time together?

Situation

A few years ago, when Philip wanted to watch YouTube videos about his favourite game, his mother, Anna, **allowed him to use her account on the platform.**

However, now she is starting to get annoyed that the platform, instead of suggesting her favourite yoga channels, recommends videos similar to those subscribed to by her son. She is considering letting her 11-year-old create his own YouTube account. What are the advantages and disadvantages of this solution?

Questions for

the family

- **Which option is safer?** Which is more convenient? Why?
- What are the **advantages** (aside from safety issues) and **disadvantages** of the mother **seeing the channels** her son subscribes to?
- What are the **advantages** (apart from more personalised recommendations) and **disadvantages** of allowing the son to **create his own YouTube account**?
- In your opinion, **what should the regulations look like** regarding allowing **teenagers to create their own accounts** on platforms like YouTube? Should it be prohibited or allowed?

Situation

Alexander, Rosalia, Sophia and Jan **are driving on holiday**. Sophia connects her Spotify account to the car speakers and plays rap music. Her mother likes it too, but Alexander and Jan can't stand it.

The women suggest that father and son put on headphones and listen to their favourite music or podcasts instead.

Questions for the family

- Do you think this is a **good solution**?
What advantages and disadvantages do you see in it?
- **What other solution** could this family come up with?
- **Who do you think should decide** what to listen to in the car, and how?
- What could help your family find a good solution **if you found yourselves** in a similar situation?

DIMENSION 05

Health

Situation

Sophia has turned 16 years old, and is now automatically assigned the **responsibility for her own health** in the governmental health platform. This means her **parents no longer have access to her health data**.

Sophia would like her parents to continue to have access and have the opportunity to book doctor's appointments for her.

Her mum Rosalía, however, believes Sophia should do so herself now that the platform has mandated that she should be in charge herself.

Questions for the family

- Family members' wishes and what platforms suggest families should do, **don't necessarily align**. How can your family deal with this?
- How can the above situation be related to an 11-year-old who wants Snapchat **before they are old enough**?

Situation

Grandma Olga has Alzheimer's, and her two children, Alexander and Anna, **want to keep her tracked 24/7 using Google Maps**, but Alexander prefers not to use geolocation.

Questions for

the family

- Why do you think Alexander **doesn't** want to use geolocation?
- **Who** should make the decision in this situation, if Grandma Olga is unable to do so?

Situation

Both Anton (grandfather), Alexander (father), and Sophia (daughter) use a **fitness platform that allows them to share fitness-related activities.**

Alexander and Sophia follow each other on the platform, allowing them to share information about how fast they have run certain routes etc. Alexander and Sophia want to follow Anton and have him follow them, but **Anton prefers not to follow nor be followed** by the younger generations in the family.

Questions for the family

- What can be the advantages of following each other on fitness platforms?
- Why might Anton **not want to follow or be followed** by his son and granddaughter?

Situation

When Olga started to show symptoms of Alzheimer's, the family wanted to **create a group chat to discuss how to best help her** and who should help her how and when.

The family, however, are struggling to decide which platform they should use for this.

Questions for the family

→ **Which platform** might be ideal for sharing health-related information, and which platforms should the family avoid using?

DIMENSION 06

Learning

Situation

Anna has a mother named Olga.

Olga does not like that so many things have become technological, because she does not feel that she can master them.

Olga will often call Anna to have her help her do things like log into her bank, set up her phone or order a doctor's appointment. Anna is a part time single mother. In addition, Anna works a fulltime job. Sometimes Anna gets annoyed when her mother calls for help.

Questions for the family

- What do you think **Olga is feeling** when she calls Anna?
- How do you think it feels for Olga that **so many things have become technological?**
- Why do you think Anna sometimes **gets annoyed when Olga calls her** for help?
- **Who should help Olga** navigate all the technology she has to deal with?

Situation

Until now Philip has been using the family tablet, but now that **he has turned 11 he is asking for a mobile phone**, so that his parents cannot see what he watches on YouTube.

Questions for

the family

- **What do you think** about Philip's proposal?
- What can be done so that **Philip has privacy when browsing the internet**, but the family can still support him?

Situation

Philip is doing homework at home. He's studying recycling and wildlife conservation. **His teacher used an app to facilitate communication between school and family.** She asked parents to identify the recycling practices at home during a week.

Questions for

the family

- What do you think of these kinds of practices that suppose a **collaboration between school and family**?
- How **can families support** school?
- Are you using **digital platforms to communicate with school**? What do you think about that? What's the main strengths and limitations according to your experience?

Situation

The Fernandez family bought a tablet recently. The father, Alexander, discovered a digital platform linked to language and literacy educational content. They are very interested in learning English, and decided to use it with his daughter Sophia. **They really enjoyed learning together.**

Questions for

the family

- **What do you think** about Sophia's decision?
- Have you ever used **digital platforms to learn** things together in the family?

THANKS FOR PLAYING!

Want to know

more?

Research key

results

The PlatFAMs research project shows how our everyday family lives are deeply shaped by digital platforms: from watching series in the living room to using maps, messaging apps, or parental controls.

These platforms not only organize our activities but also collect data and shape our behavior through algorithms, something that rises concerns and debates in families.

Some of the project's main results are outlined under **the following topics** (see next page).

Digital Care

Family intimacy through platforms varies between families, with some relying heavily on technology and others only partially. Many families set rules to protect screen-free family time.

Typical practices include children using platforms mainly for leisure and socializing, grandparents to maintain family connections, and parents for tasks and caregiving. Platforms like WhatsApp allow closeness, support, and safety, although they can sometimes fragment attention.

Surveillance & Trust

Families, particularly parents and children, **use platforms that involve sharing locations and tracking activities.**

This “family interveillance” is seen by some as part of care and transparency,

but many are concerned about data tracking and how their information may be used. As a result, some families resist platform-based surveillance, prioritizing privacy and autonomy.

Routines and shared leisure

Streaming platforms like Netflix, YouTube, or Spotify are part of daily family life. **Sharing series or music creates closeness, conversation, and joint experiences.** However, differences in age, tastes, or schedules can complicate family interactions. Platform design decisions, such as personalized recommendations or account restrictions, also influence how families experience these shared activities.

PlatFAMs shows that living a family life today means navigating a complex digital ecosystem together. Technology provides support, connection, and entertainment, but it also raises challenges around privacy, attention, and family life.

Understanding these dynamics can help families make more conscious and balanced choices in an increasingly digital world.

To learn more, visit:

<https://digitalfamilies.eu/>

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